

How do nuclear star clusters form?

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As their name suggests, nuclear star clusters (NSCs) are dense star clusters located in the nuclei of galaxies. NSCs have masses between $10^5 - 10^8 M_{\odot}$ and half-light radii of $3 - 10$ pc (see the recent review [1] and references therein), making them among the densest stellar systems in the Universe with densities that can even surpass those of globular clusters (GCs).

Photometric studies of large samples of galaxies have established that at least 70% of all galaxies have an NSC in their centre (e.g., [2, 3, 4]). This nucleation fraction is a function of galaxy mass and peaks at $M_{\text{gal}} \approx 10^9 M_{\odot}$, where more than 80% of all galaxies are nucleated, while less than 10% of galaxies with masses below $10^6 M_{\odot}$ or above $10^{11} M_{\odot}$ host an NSC [5, 6].

NSCs often co-exist with supermassive black holes, for example in the Milky Way, and they seem to follow similar scaling relations that connect their properties to properties of the host galaxy (e.g., [7, 8, 9, 10, 5]). The existence of such relations connecting vastly different spatial scales hints towards a connected evolution of the NSC and its host galaxy, but the formation mechanisms of NSCs and their dependence on galaxy properties are debated.

Formation mechanisms

In general, two pathways for NSC formation are discussed: the in-situ formation scenario, where the NSC forms at the galaxy's centre from infalling pre-enriched gas (e.g., [11, 13]), and the gas-free merger of GCs that spiral inwards due to dynamical friction (e.g., [14, 15, 16]). Also composite scenarios have been proposed and most likely both channels are realised in Nature [17, 1], but their relative contributions in different galactic environments are still unclear.

The two NSC formation channels impart different expectations for the stellar population properties of the NSC in comparison to the host galaxy and the GCs. In the GC accretion scenario, the NSC should reflect the stellar populations of the accreted GCs, explaining the old, metal-poor stellar populations of NSCs in some dwarf early-type galaxies [18, 19]. In contrast, the in-situ formation channel is usually invoked to explain the presence of young stars, extended star formation histories with multiple star forming episodes and metal-rich populations that exceed the metallicity of the host galaxy [20]. Constraining the dominant NSC formation channel therefore requires a panoramic view of the stellar population properties (ages, metallicities, star formation histories) of the NSC in comparison to the stellar body of the host galaxy and the GCs. The Multi Unit Spectroscopic Explorer (MUSE), an integral-field spectrograph mounted at ESO's Very Large Telescope in Chile, allows such a simultaneous study of all the involved components.

Comparing a massive and a dwarf galaxy

To explore NSC formation in different galactic environ-

ment, it is illustrative to first consider individual case studies. Here, we compare the massive early-type galaxy FCC47 ($M_{\text{gal}} \approx 10^{10} M_{\odot}$) in the Fornax galaxy cluster ($D \approx 20$ Mpc) to the dwarf galaxy KK197 ($M_{\text{gal}} \approx 10^7 M_{\odot}$) which is a satellite of Centaurus A at a distance of ≈ 4 Mpc. Both galaxies span roughly the same extent on the sky and are nucleated, but the NSC in FCC47 has a mass of $\approx 7 \times 10^8 M_{\odot}$, while KK197 hosts a low-mass NSC with $M_{\text{NSC}} \approx 10^6 M_{\odot}$.

Analysis of the MUSE data of both galaxies shows further differences (see [21] and [18]). FCC47 shows a peculiar kinematic structure and its massive NSC is kinematically decoupled, while KK197 only exhibits low-amplitude rotation. In addition, both galaxies show different radial metallicity profiles (Figure 1). While the NSC in FCC47 is the most metal-rich component in the galaxy, the NSC of KK197 is significantly more metal-poor than the galaxy and shares the low metallicity of a nearby GC.

Figure 1: Radial metallicity profiles of FCC47 (top) and KK197 (bottom), showing the metallicities of NSCs (blue stars) and GCs (pink circles) in comparison to the stars (orange). The data quality of KK197 was insufficient to get a profile, so the dashed line shows the average value. Adapted from [21] and [18].

These results indicate that these two NSCs were formed through different formation processes. The low-mass, metal-poor NSC shares many of its properties with typical metal-poor GCs and, hence, is likely the product of the GC accretion scenario. In contrast, forming the massive, metal-rich and kinematically decoupled NSC of FCC47 through metal-poor, low-mass GCs seems unlikely. It is probable the result of efficient in-situ star formation, although the kinematically decoupled nature indi-

cates that this NSC was further shaped by a merger process that has altered the kinematic structure of FCC 47.

A trend with galaxy mass?

The two case studies therefore illustrate that both processes are realised in Nature, but possibly in different galactic environments. Hence, to test whether there exists a dependence of the dominant NSC formation channel with galaxy properties, we can investigate a larger sample of 25 early-type galaxies in the Fornax and Virgo galaxy clusters with similar techniques (see [22]).

A background-cleaned extraction of the NSC spectra enables us to compare their stellar population properties to the underlying host galaxy. Metallicity profiles similar to those presented in Figure 1 can be used to identify metal-poor NSCs and by including also information on stellar ages, young populations indicative of ongoing in-situ formation are detected. In addition, star formation histories (SFHs) of the NSCs reveal more detail in comparison to the host galaxies (Figure 2). For example, while the SFHs of the massive galaxy FCC 170 and its NSC only show a single old and metal-rich component, the NSC SFH of the dwarf galaxy FCC 202 shows a minor metal-rich and young population in addition to a dominating old and metal-poor component. These two populations directly indicate that both NSC formation channels have acted in the assembly of this NSC.

Figure 2: SFHs of the NSCs (top) and the host galaxy (bottom) of two galaxies, FCC 170 and FCC 202. Each bin is coloured by the mean metallicity. Adapted from [22].

Based on such stellar population analysis, it is possible to explore trends of the dominant NSC formation channel with galaxy and NSC mass, as shown in Figure 3. This figure clearly reveals that the dominant NSC formation channel changes from GC accretion to in-situ star formation with increasing galaxy and NSC mass. Low-mass NSCs in low-mass galaxies form predominantly through the merger of GCs as evident from their

low metallicities, whereas high-mass NSCs located in massive galaxies assembled most of their mass through in-situ processes. This transition appears to happen at NSC masses $\approx 10^7 M_{\odot}$ and galaxy masses of $\approx 10^9 M_{\odot}$, and there are several galaxies at intermediate masses where both channels appear to have played a significant role in the formation of their NSC.

Figure 3: Galaxy versus NSC mass for the studied galaxies. Symbols indicate the dominant NSC formation channel as identified from stellar population analysis. Adapted from [22].

Although restricted to a small sample of 25 early-type galaxies, these results are fundamental for understanding NSC formation and their potential as unique probes of the evolutionary history of galaxy centres. The work presented in this talk lay the basis for future studies exploring NSC in different environments or galaxy types.

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